

A Survey of Internet of Things and Big Data Integrated Solutions for Industrie 4.0

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Abstract—The industrial internet of things (IIoT) is growing at an exponential rate generating massive amounts of industrial data. This data must be leveraged to support business and operational goals. As a result, there is an urgent need for adopting big data technologies to enable data analytics in industrial automation. This paper explores interrelations between IIoT and big data technologies and how they work together to generate business insights from industrial data. Additionally, requirements for cloud-based solutions are derived from the Industrie 4.0 use case scenario value-based-services, focusing on condition monitoring and predictive maintenance services. A survey of selected cloud-based platforms is conducted to examine how these platforms meet the requirements derived from the use case. Results show that existing general cloud platforms should adopt more IIoT applications and platforms, while existing industrial cloud platforms should add big data frameworks to their portfolio. Finally, an architecture for integrating cloud-based IIoT and big data solutions is introduced and issues regarding the use of public cloud for IIoT applications are discussed.

Index Terms—Big Data, Cloud Computing, Internet of Things (IoT), Industrial IoT (IIoT), Industrie 4.0, Industrial Automation

I. INTRODUCTION

In response to the Industrie 4.0 trend of increasing the connectivity of *things* and building smart industrial systems, cloud computing has become widely used in industrial automation to provide flexible and on-demand infrastructure for industrial services [1]. The industrial internet of things (IIoT) and its applications are continuously increasing. Therefore, the integration of IIoT and cloud computing is urgently needed to exploit the capabilities of cloud resources and technologies. Given that the huge amount of non-structured and semi-structured data produced by IIoT, big data technologies have become an imperative necessity to address data issues such as distribution, parallel processing, analytics, visualization, etc. [2].

As a result, cloud computing, IIoT, and big data are being considered as interdependent technologies that can make a big change not only in industrial automation but in all industry sectors. Nevertheless, there is still much ambiguity regarding the role played by each technology and how they interact with each other to improve industrial automation. In addition, hundreds of cloud service providers claim to be providing IoT

and big data as a service for business and industry. However, these platforms vary in their potential and in the level of supporting IoT and big data solutions and there is no standard process to identify a suitable cloud platform for industrial automation purposes.

This paper discusses the roles of cloud, IoT, and big data technologies and how they can be combined to provide integrated solutions to improve industrial operations. The paper introduces requirements that must be considered when choosing IIoT and big data solutions for industrial automation. However, the main goal of this paper is to identify the gap between IoT and big data solutions and to define the challenges of using these technologies in Industrie 4.0 factories. To better understand the current situation of the available cloud-based IoT and big data solutions, a survey of selected examples of cloud service platforms is conducted to assess their ability to provide IoT and big data solutions with a high level of integration.

This paper is organized as follows. Section II presents a literature review of related technologies. Section III introduces requirements that must be evaluated against IoT and big data solutions in industrial automation. Section IV presents the survey conducted on selected cloud platforms solutions and discusses the survey results. A conceptual integrated architecture of IIoT and big data solutions is introduced in Section V with an actual example platform. Finally, the conclusion and future work are presented in Section VI.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Cloud Computing

According to the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) "*cloud computing is a model for enabling ubiquitous, convenient, on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources (e.g. networks, servers, storage, applications, and services) that can be rapidly provisioned and released with minimal management effort or service provider interaction*". The cloud computing model includes five characteristics, three service models, and four deployment models [3].

The essential characteristics include:

- *On-demand self-service*: A consumer can provision additional computing resources as needed without human interaction with the service provider.
- *Broad network access*: The possibility to reach all services and resources via the Internet using heterogeneous terminal devices.
- *Resource pooling*: Cloud resources including storage, processing, memory, network, and virtual machines are shared among multiple users using a multi-tenant model to increase resources utilization and to reduce costs.
- *Rapid elasticity*: Cloud resources can be scaled out on demand and without the need to refer to the service provider. From a user point of view, cloud resources appear to be unlimited and can be obtained at any time in any quantity.
- *Measured service*: A cloud consumer may only pay for resources that are used [3], [4].

The architecture of cloud computing can be classified into four operational layers as shown in Fig. 1. However, from service perspective, these layers can be grouped into three service models as follows:

- 1) *Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS)* provides physical and virtual infrastructure resources by combining the hardware and infrastructure layers. Usually, resources at the hardware layer including processors, storage devices, and networks are managed by the service provider. However, infrastructure resources such as virtual machines (VMs), operating systems, and virtual networking are controlled by the consumer [3], [5].
- 2) *Platform as a Service (PaaS)* provides resources at the platform layer including operating systems, software development frameworks, and database engines.
- 3) *Software as a Service (SaaS)* provides on-demand applications and web services to end users over the Internet.

Fig. 1. Cloud Computing Architecture [5]

Cloud services are categorized based on the ownership, access, and control into four deployment models: (1) *public cloud*: a cloud service is available to public users over the Internet and is owned and operated by the cloud service provider; (2) *private cloud*: a cloud service is exclusively available for a

single organization and it is managed by the organization or a third party operator. The infrastructure resources may exist on-premise or off-premise; (3) *community cloud*: a cloud infrastructure is established and shared by several cloud service customers; (4) *hybrid cloud*: a cloud service that combines two or more cloud deployment models. Appropriate technologies are involved to enable data and application portability between different base clouds [3], [6].

B. Big Data

The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) defines big data as "extensive datasets – primarily in the characteristics of volume, variety, velocity, and/or variability – that require a scalable architecture for efficient storage, manipulation, and analysis" [7]. As mentioned in the definition, big data is often described by the characteristics *Volume* (huge amount of data), *Variety* (many different types of sources and formats), *Velocity* (the flow of data is continuous and massive), and *Variability* (continuous change in data rate, form, semantics, and quality). These requirements lead to a new paradigm of data management whose idea revolves around data and processing distribution across horizontal loosely-coupled resources to achieve high performance and to deliver business insights from large-scale datasets [7], [8].

A big data platform is an Information Technology (IT) solution that combines the features and capabilities of big data frameworks and applications within a single solution to enable companies to collect, store, manage, analyze, and visualize massive volumes of data at high speed and scalable manner [9], [10].

The main challenges in big data systems lie in: 1) capturing huge amounts of data from multiple sources with different syntax and semantics, 2) preparing data for analysis through multiple stages such as validation, cleaning, transformation, indexing, aggregation, and storing, and 3) choosing the appropriate processing technique that fits to the nature of data and business requirements. It can be batch processing, where data is collected over time and then sent for processing, or real-time processing, where data is usually fed piece by piece in real-time [9].

C. Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT)

IIoT is changing the world by connecting sensors, actuators, controllers, and computers through the Internet to exchange information and thus to deliver intelligent services [11]. It covers a very wide range of application areas such as smart home, smart city, smart grid, agriculture, smart manufacturing, transportation systems, e-Health, and so on [12].

Manufacturing companies are currently implementing the IIoT technology for intelligent connectivity of devices in different industrial applications. To distinguish these applications from the general IIoT applications, the term *Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT)* is often used [13], [14].

The Industrial Internet Consortium introduced a reference architecture of IIoT comprising three tiers: edge, platform, and enterprise tier, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The edge tier collects

data from edge nodes through edge gateways and transfer it to the platform tier which in turn provides management functions for assets and offers data operations and analytics. Finally, the enterprise tier provides interfaces to end-users and implements applications and decision support systems [15].

In order to reduce the amount of transferred data and hence computing efforts at the platform and enterprise tier, IoT devices may use embedded smart sensor systems. Such compact systems integrate preprocessing mechanisms that calibrate, filter, amplify, linearize or compensate the original sensor signal depending on the particular use case. IoT devices that contain multiple sensor units may apply sensor fusion to provide either redundancy or a combined interpretation of captured data, e.g. pattern recognition applications [16]. Communication between

Fig. 2. Three-Tier Industrial Internet of Things System Architecture [17].

industrial devices and other systems is one of the industrial automation challenges because of the special requirements of speed, reliability, flexibility, and knowledge extraction. Common IIoT protocols are: Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP), Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) as a message-oriented protocol, Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP) as a specialized web transfer protocol, Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP) as an open standard application layer protocol for message-oriented middleware, and OPC Unified Architecture (OPC UA), the next generation OPC standard that provides secure and reliable access to real-time and historical data and events [18]–[20].

D. Industrie 4.0

Industrie 4.0 is a German initiative that aims to increase intelligent communication and integration between production and logistics processes to achieve a high level of efficiency and flexibility in manufacturing industry [1], [21], [22]. The main standardization results of Industrie 4.0 are the Reference Architecture Model Industrie 4.0 (RAMI 4.0) and the I4.0 Component. RAMI 4.0 is a three-dimensional layered architecture that combines all elements and IT components in a structured manner. However, the I4.0 Component is a unified model that describes how real and virtual objects communicate with other Industrie 4.0 components. It comprises two elements: Asset and Asset Administration Shell (AAS), see Fig. 3. AAS is a virtual representation of the asset. It stores

information about the asset and describes the communication interface for interacting with other Industrie 4.0 assets [21]–[23].

Fig. 3. I4.0 Component [24]

E. Interrelation Between Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) and Big Data

Generating continuous data from a huge number of IIoT devices and sensors leads to a rapid increase of data that the enterprise needs to manage, process, and analyze [25]. That makes IIoT a major source of big data and motivates further development in big data technologies and applications to meet the requirements of industrial fields [25], [26]. In contrast, big data facilitates data management, processing, and analytics to deliver IIoT business value to the enterprise.

Fig. 4 shows that IIoT focuses on industrial devices and their communication to produce vast amounts of data. However, big data provides frameworks for data distribution and parallel processing that support IIoT data analysis and visualization [25], [27]. As a result of adapting Industrie 4.0 principles

Fig. 4. Interrelation between IIoT and Big Data.

in the manufacturing industry, processes should become more flexible and efficient than before by taking advantage of the emerging information transparency. However, the produced data becomes more intensive and complex to be stored and analyzed by traditional technologies. Therefore, there is a broad consensus that big data and IIoT technologies are tightly interrelated and should evolve cooperatively [26].

III. REQUIREMENTS FOR CLOUD-BASED SOLUTIONS IN INDUSTRIAL AUTOMATION

Investigating the features and potentials of cloud solutions and making the decision to select the suitable cloud provider

is not a trivial task. Even worse, changing to another provider will be very complex and expensive if it was chosen in an arbitrary process. However, the most important step before evaluating alternative solutions is to identify the requirements that must be met by a given cloud platform.

The manufacturing industry has special requirements that make it distinct from other industry sectors. This section presents requirements to be considered in evaluating and choosing cloud-based big data and IoT solutions for industrial data analytics.

- **Scalability**

When speaking about IIoT and big data, scalability is crucial since the exponential growth of connected devices and data generated in industrial fields need expandable resources and distribution technologies that can horizontally scale out to meet customer needs [15].

- **Low Latency**

Industrial operations have to be carried out in real-time. Therefore, industrial applications and networks must provide a guarantee of service to fulfill these operations deterministically [1], [28].

- **Security**

Security is a serious issue in cloud computing and is one of the main concerns behind the resistance of many companies to move their applications or data to cloud [29]. A disruption of a manufacturing process or attacking the electrical system of a manufacturing plant results in a great financial loss. Therefore, cloud service providers must provide security techniques for authentication, authorization, data encryption, event logging, and so on. Moreover, a cloud solution must comply with the IT security standards and certifications such as ISO/IEC 27001-2 [30].

- **Supported Protocols**

IIoT protocols supported by a cloud solution must be considered by the consumer. It is also worth considering which protocols the customer/provider is working on to use/support in future to align with the current trend of Industrie 4.0 [22].

- **Reliability**

In the manufacturing industry, critical operations need a high level of accuracy to perform their required functions under stated conditions for a specified period of time and in a specified environment. Therefore, cloud-based industrial solutions must be subject to the same conditions in order to meet the reliability requirements.

- **Integration**

Manufacturing plants have complex systems of interconnected assets, embedded applications, and operation management systems. These systems are also integrated with back-office enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems. Therefore, IIoT solutions must support integration of these systems with minimal efforts of manual configuration. Recently, there have been research to introduce a standard information model and a mechanism for dy-

namic configuration and integration of plant assets based on the standard Industrie 4.0 Asset Administration Shell interface [23], [31].

- **Pricing Models**

Cloud providers provide different price models. The most common one is the *pay-as-you-go* model [32]. Industrial networks often support tens of thousands of machines, controllers, and sensors. Therefore, a company should analyze the pricing model carefully based on the expected use since these pricing models are very tricky once a customer reaches a certain limit of connected devices or service use.

IV. SURVEY OF SELECTED CLOUD-BASED IIOT AND BIG DATA PLATFORMS

In Section III, requirements for offering cloud-based IIoT and big data solutions have been introduced. This section presents the survey that has been conducted on exemplary cloud-based IoT and big data platforms and how these solutions fit to the industrial automation requirements. It must be noticed that this survey is not about comparing service providers. However, it serves as an overview of the key features supported by these platforms regarding IoT and big data technologies.

The exemplary platforms have been selected to be mixed of general and industrial cloud platforms. Amazon AWS, IBM Cloud, Microsoft Azure, and SAP Cloud Platform are of the key players of general purpose cloud service providers [33], [34]. However, Siemens MindSphere, Bosch IoT Suite, and PTC Cloud platforms are especially built for industrial purposes [35]. The information of this survey is collected by reference to official documentations and websites as well as by direct contact with the providers. It is also based on a market study of IT platforms for IoT conducted by Fraunhofer IAO in 2017 [36].

Although the survey has addressed a wider scope of features and details, only some IoT and big data features are presented in this section due to the paper's space limitation. As shown in Table I, criteria are organized in two main sections: big data solutions and IoT solutions. The section of big data solutions includes the potential of a given platform regarding big data technologies. Criteria such as processing framework, processing mode, storage systems, databases, and data analytics are evaluated. The section of IoT solutions explores the IoT solutions names and how these solutions fulfill IoT protocols and I4.0 standardized communication, connectivity technologies (e.g. LAN, WAN, Bluetooth, Satellite, etc.), diversity of IoT applications, whether they have their own IIoT gateways that are involved in the data collection process, and edge computing technologies. The result of the survey is summarized in Table I.

Survey Results Discussion

As mentioned earlier, the goal of this survey is not to compare certain vendors but rather to have an idea about IoT and big data solutions offered on these platforms and how

TABLE I
FEATURES OF SELECTED CLOUD PLATFORMS REGARDING IOT AND BIG DATA SOLUTIONS

Criteria	AWS	IBM Cloud	MS Azure	SAP Cloud Platform	Siemens Mindsphere	Bosch IoT Suite	PTC Cloud
Main purpose	General	General	General	General	Industrial	Industrial	Industrial
Big Data Solutions							
Processing Frameworks	MapReduce, Spark, Kinesis	MapReduce, Spark	MapReduce, Spark	MapReduce, Spark	–	–	–
Processing Mode	Batch, Stream	Batch, Stream	Batch, Stream	Batch, Stream	–	–	–
Storage Systems	+	+	+	+	–	–	–
Databases	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Data analytics	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
IoT Solutions	AWS IoT	Watson IoT	Azure IoT suite	SAP IoT	MindSphere	Bosch IoT Suite	Thingworx
IIoT Protocols	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Connectivity Technologies	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
IIoT Apps	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
IIoT gateways	–	–	–	–	+	+	–
Edge Computing	+	+	+	+	+	–	–

Legend: (+) → supported, (–) → not supported or no information available

they meet the industrial automation requirements as well as to identify the gap of integrating IIoT and big data solutions. Since the survey does not include quantitative data and deep investigation, we used a tolerant rather than strict evaluation, e.g. the symbol “+” means that a service is supported by a given platform regardless of the level of support (high, med, low). Information in Table I shows that industrial IIoT cloud platforms particularly focus on IIoT communication and applications as they support many IIoT protocols, applications, and platforms. However, there is still a lack of supporting big data frameworks and applications as well as edge computing techniques.

On the other hand, general purpose cloud platforms offer a wide variety of business applications, development platforms, analytics platforms, and infrastructure resources. Additionally, they dedicate specific suites for IIoT solutions. Despite the lack of providing comprehensive IIoT solutions, there are more opportunities to integrate the IIoT suite with big data and other business solutions available on that platforms. For example, SAP Cloud Platform provides seamless integration between IIoT applications, HANA-based analytics, and SAP Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system.

Considering the requirements introduced in Section III, public cloud would be a good choice when a customer does not want (or does not have the experience) to manage hardware or software resources. Additionally, it allows IIoT solutions to integrate with other solutions available on the same cloud platform. Nevertheless, issues such as latency and security remain a source of serious concern for industry operators to use public cloud. Many IIoT cloud providers have reduced these concerns by providing fog and edge computing that allow IIoT time-critical applications to have their data processed closer to devices rather than sending it to the cloud [1], more details about fog computing in Section V-B.

In contrast, on-premise solutions enable full control over resources and security as well as minimizing data transmission costs and latency. These solutions are also suitable when a

business is expected to grow fast since public cloud will become more expensive once a certain number of devices or requests is exceeded. However, a company has to pay for infrastructure resources and to bear administrative and operating responsibilities. Additionally, local platforms often include less applications and services which means new applications must be developed locally or integrated from other providers. The optimum solution would be for an industrial company to integrate both cloud and on-premise solutions to achieve maximum benefit and to minimize disadvantages of both. However, the main challenge in this scenario is the integration process.

V. INTEGRATED PLATFORM FOR INDUSTRIAL IIoT AND BIG DATA SOLUTIONS

Big data generated by IIoT needs expandable infrastructure with distribution technologies to achieve high scalability, availability, and performance [26]. In addition, there is a need for having on-demand and as-requested resources at a much lower cost according to the actual usage without the need to own the resources or to bear the burden of administration and maintenance issues [26], [29]. Cloud computing plays a key role to meet these requirements and to provide big data and IIoT solutions as a service [37]. A survey regarding big data and cloud strategy reports that 84% of targeted companies emphasized that having all big data analytics technologies in one platform from a single vendor is important to move their data and applications to cloud [29].

In summary, integrating cloud computing, IIoT, and big data technologies will drive meaningful impact on the Industrie 4.0 community.

A. Cloud-based Industrial IIoT and Big Data Architecture

The survey results presented in Section IV shows that there is a need for integrating IIoT and big data solutions in one platform. To this end, this section introduces an architecture that combines cloud, IIoT, and big data technologies for industrial

automation. Fig. 5 illustrates the architecture components and how they interact with each other as well as the dependencies and overlaps between them. At the IaaS layer, cloud computing

Fig. 5. Cloud-based Industrial IoT and Big Data Architecture [15], [38]

provides the infrastructure of physical and virtual resources to host the components at the upper layers. This layer is managed and maintained by cloud administrators. At the upper layer, big data provides two types of frameworks: storage and computation frameworks. Storage frameworks provide a platform for data distribution and organization. However, processing frameworks provide software that supports distributed computation. There are two main processing modes supported in big data: batch and real-time (stream) modes. However, given the need to access live data of production devices, stream processing has great importance in industrial automation.

The top layer of the big data stack consists of applications and services that encapsulate the business logic and functionality to be executed by interacting with the underlying big data frameworks. Big data applications and services include activities such as data collection, preparation, analytics, access, and visualization [38]. Recall Fig. 2, the main purpose of IIoT is to manage devices at the edge layer, connect them together, and collect data from them. The huge amounts of data being produced from the IIoT edge tier certainly need big data techniques for data management, processing, and analytics. Therefore, cooperation between IIoT and big data occurs by taking advantage of big data frameworks and applications to store, process, analyze, and visualize industrial big data acquired by IIoT. Essential aspects including security, distribution, scalability, and flexibility must be addressed across the whole architecture.

B. Fog Computing: Connecting the Cloud to Things

Due to the rapid growth of data generated by IIoT, moving such huge data to could be inefficient and result in latency issues which will affect the quality of the IIoT applications. To cope with these challenges, fog computing has emerged as a recent paradigm shift in computing where storage, computation, and analysis are provided closer to the data sources and users [39].

Fog computing is a middle layer between the cloud and IIoT

devices. It supports low-latency network connections between devices and analytics endpoints and reduces the network traffic between IIoT devices and cloud platforms. It also overcomes other issues of public cloud such as availability, security, and control. This section presents the architecture of the Lab Big Data at Fraunhofer IOSB-INA as an example of a fog computing platform.

Fraunhofer IOSB-INA Lab Big Data in SmartFactoryOWL

Fraunhofer IOSB-INA in Lemgo has set up the Lab Big Data for the purpose of research and development of big data solutions in industrial automation. These solutions are supposed to have a great impact on products and process optimization. The Lab Big Data maintains a live access to real-time data produced by machines, devices, and facilities in the SmartFactoryOWL (a joint initiative of the Fraunhofer-society and the OWL University of Applied Sciences that includes a production environment with real systems of assembly and production machines connected via IIoT technology) [40], see Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Fraunhofer IOSB-INA Lab Big Data and SmartFactoryOWL

Machine learning algorithms are used to discover hidden patterns and correlations between things, processes, and events in production plants. Based on these patterns, different industrial applications including anomaly detection, predictive maintenance, material flow optimization, and energy consumption optimization can be achieved [40]. For example, a transportation profile of delivering an item from point A to point B within a plant can be analyzed regarding energy consumption. As a result, an alternative profile could be detected and recommended to be used for less energy consumption. In terms of predictive maintenance, many parameters including temperature, positioning, and overload errors can be collected, analyzed, and monitored in real-time to predict the need for maintenance before the situation becomes critical.

Big Data Processing Architecture

The data processing architecture of the Lab Big Data, as shown in Fig. 6, complies to the Lambda Architecture [41] as a generic, distributed, scalable, and fault-tolerant big data processing architecture which is able to serve a wide range of workloads by taking advantage of both batch and

stream processing modes. At the same time, it implements the conceptual architecture introduced in Section V-A on a local infrastructure.

Live data produced by the SmartFactoryOWL machines and devices including pressure, temperature, voltage, current, position, etc. is acquired using different IIoT protocols, aggregated through gateways, and sent to the Lab Big Data for processing and analysis.

Data is received by Apache Kafka [42], a distributed pub-sub real-time messaging system that provides strong message durability and fault tolerance guarantees. Kafka cluster in turn logs the received data in distributed and replicated topics to make them ready for subscribers (consumers). For stream processing, data is directly consumed and processed by Apache Storm [43], a distributed real-time computation system. However, for batch processing, it is stored to Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) or a time series database such as KairosDB [44] or OpenTSDB [45] to be analyzed later using Hadoop MapReduce [46] or Apache Spark [47].

In addition to the data analysis libraries supported by the computation frameworks, data scientists at Fraunhofer IOSB-INA develop machine learning algorithms in R and Python to adapt to different industrial data analytics use cases.

Finally, microservices on the enterprise layer such as visual analytics, data mining, and decision making support can access the production data. The next step is to integrate this platform with public cloud platforms to take advantage of further analytics and centralized data solutions for non-critical applications.

Overcome Issues

As already mentioned, public cloud infrastructures are still facing challenges in terms of latency, security, and the integration of IIoT and big data solutions [1]. The Lab Big Data addresses these issues as follows:

Low Latency: The Lab Big Data is located next to the production field and is supported with high speed networking. Additionally, the cluster has compatible hardware and high data transmission interfaces. Moreover, the big data solutions used such as Kafka and Storm are distinguished by delivering results with less latency. As a result, the whole solution can certainly support better network performance and lower latency compared to public cloud platforms.

Full control: Unlike public cloud platforms, the Lab Big Data offers full control over sensitive production data, security, and resources since it has dedicated resources on dedicated physical infrastructure.

Integration: Basically, the main goal of the Lab Big Data is to bring big data solutions to the industrial automation field. The interaction between SmartFactoryOWL and the Lab Big Data realizes the integration of IIoT and big data solutions.

Availability: The big data cluster is designed to ensure high availability of service at different levels. It supports redundant physical servers and network devices as well as storage devices with RAID technology. It also supports redundancy and fail-over at the virtual level of nodes and networking. Additionally,

all software frameworks used including Hadoop, Kafka, Storm, and Spark are supported with fault-tolerant technology.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In the context of Industrie 4.0, the future vision is how to consolidate IoT and big data technologies to help the manufacturing industry to improve production operations and to achieve a high level of efficiency and cost reduction. This paper identifies special requirements for industrial automation that must be met when choosing a cloud solution. A survey of selected cloud platforms is conducted to examine their capabilities to provide integrated IIoT and big data solutions. The results show that there is no exclusive IoT and big data platform and conclusively it depends on requirements and use cases. They also show that many industrial cloud platforms need to be extended to include big data frameworks and solutions. Conversely, general cloud platforms need to adopt more IoT connectivity and applications. Finally, the paper introduces an integrated architecture that combines IIoT and big data solutions in one platform with an example of a real implementation.

Although the survey also includes information regarding latency, performance, and scalability of the considered platforms, this information is not presented in this paper due to the uncertainty of its accuracy, since it is only sourced from the providers' documentation and websites. Therefore, the future work is to design a robust test-case that can be used to accurately measure the capabilities of IoT cloud platforms against latency, cycle time, scalability, and costs. The test-case could use IoT intelligent simulators to create thousands of virtual IoT endpoints that generate big data to a target cloud platform for assessment.

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